

The Influence of Self-Concept on Deviant Behaviour in the Students of Ternate State Islamic Institute

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study was to analyze the influence of self-concept on deviant behaviour in the students of Ternate State Islamic Institute. The scope was limited to three problems, they were: 1) Self-concept of students of Ternate State Islamic Institute. 2) The deviant behaviour of students of the Ternate State Islamic Institute. 3) The significance level of self-concept influence on student's deviant behaviour at the Ternate State Islamic Institute. This type of research was field research with a survey approach and psychological sampling technique by using a sampling quota of 77 people. The research instruments were questionnaire and documentation. The analysis techniques were descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. The results showed that: 1) the students' self-concept of Ternate State Islamic Institute was in the medium category, it was 57%. 2) The students' deviant behaviour of Ternate State Islamic Institute was in a low category, it was 8%. Self-concept has a significant effect on deviant behaviour among students of Ternate State Islamic Institute which was 14.5%.

INTRODUCTION

Student behaviour is greatly influenced by knowledge, attitudes and experiences in life which is developed through the potential given by Allah SWT. This behaviour is a spiritual expression of a person as a description of his faith (Burga 2019b). Therefore, one of the most important potentials to be preserved and maintained in humans is the potential of faith (Agus 2020), because, In essence, every human being on this earth is certainly born with a potential known as the nature of monotheism (Burga 2019a).

According to Khon (2012), the attitude and character of students are very important things to be known by the educator. Students faced informal educational institutions have their characteristics that have been formed from different household or community environments. Some are good and some are bad; some are obedient and some are disobedient; some like to violate school rules and some obey the rules.

This assumption motivates lecturers to study the psychology of their students. In the world of campus, it is often found that a lecturer responds to students or justifies students as

lazy, naughty, and several other terms that have negative connotations. This happens because students sometimes violate the student code of ethics.

This phenomenon for the writer is a natural thing because, in essence, there are two inherent traits in humans, namely good and bad qualities. In the reality of social life, sometimes at a certain moment, the person has good behaviour, but on other occasions, he behaves badly.

Makbuloh (2012) stated that good and bad are contradictory and two opposites can't unite at the same time, except to become the third nature. For example, if hot and cold are put together at the same time and place, they are not hot and not cold, but warm. Warm is its characteristic that differs in levels from hot or cold. Day and night will not be united but there is between the two. Likewise humans, in him there are good qualities and bad qualities. But these traits are only potential things. Based on the potential they have, humans must form themselves. The ability to shape himself is a uniquely human ability, which is not shared by other creatures.

The behaviour of students at the Ternate State Islamic Institute is very diverse, some are well behaved and some are behaving defiantly. Deviant behaviour in this context is a violation of the student code of ethics. According to Agus (IAIN Ternate Lecturer), several factors that cause deviant behaviour in IAIN Ternate students are divided into two factors, namely internal and external factors. Internal factors are causes that occur due to problems within the student himself, while external factors are causes that occur due to problems from outside the students themselves and maybe a combination of internal factors and external factors.

Factors from within students are related to their understanding of themselves or their self-awareness. Meanwhile, factors from outside students are influenced by the people around them, including friends in an organization (Idris & Usman 2019).

Referring to these empirical facts, it can be seen that the factors causing deviant behaviour in IAIN Ternate students are understanding or awareness of students' self (self-concept). The term self-concept is usually interpreted as an understanding of self. According to Desmita (2013), understanding of self (sense of self) is a structure that helps children organize and understand who they are, which is based on the views of others, their own experiences and the basis of cultural classifications such as gender, race and so on. The factors that influence self-concept are as follows: 1) physical image factor; 2) meaningful feeling factor; 3) self-actualization factor; 4) experience factor; 5) the benevolence factor; 6) competency factor; and 7) social role factors (Astuti 2015).

Several factors that influence this self-concept can influence behaviour or morale. If these factors are well maintained, it will form good morals too, but if they are not maintained properly, it will also form bad morals.

This assumption is confirmed by Alang (2014) that the decline in human morality is increasingly becoming a concern. As if this phenomenon could no longer be stopped. This moral decadence affects not only the nation's young generation but also to the elderly. Seeing this situation, surely it becomes the duty and obligation of all humans to straighten out human morals which are increasingly deteriorating.

According to Myers (2012), self-concept is determined by many influences, including the role they have, self-comparison, self-social identity, self-perception towards others about self-assessment, and experiences of success and failure that have been experienced. Self-esteem motivation influences cognitive processes. In the face of failure, people with high self-esteem maintain their self-worth by thinking that people who failed will show high enthusiasm for others to be better.

Meanwhile, according to Yusuf and Nurihsan (2005), the factors that affect a person's personality can be divided into two, namely: 1) Internal factors are factors that originated from the younger generation itself or the person's condition. Some are in the form of physical factors such as physical disabilities, stunting, excessive obesity and others. There are also psychic things such as stuttering speech, daydreaming, sexual disorders, always being anxious and so on. 2) External factors are the factors originated from outside the person's self, which more popularly termed as the environmental factors. These factors include the physical, social, cultural, economic, political and other environments.

Internal factors that come from the younger generation are physical and non-physical (Santrock 2011). The term youth in psychology is defined as the transition from adolescence to adulthood. For most individuals, becoming an adult involves a long transition period. The recent transition from adolescence to adulthood is referred to as emerging adulthood that occurs from 18 years of age to 25 years. This period is marked by experimentation and exploration at this point in a person's development, many individuals are still exploring the career path they want to take, what kind of individual they want to be, how life is faced and what kind of lifestyle they want, for example choosing to live single, live together and get married.

So, the ages of 18 to 25 years are the ages of students who are becoming adults. In other words, adolescents who turn into adulthood tend to show their identity, so that sometimes they have a self-concept that is less controllable.

Based on the phenomenon that has been described, it indicated that the factor that influenced student behaviour was self-concept, so the problem have been discussed was the influence of self-concept on deviant behaviour of students at the Ternate State Islamic Institute.

RESEARCH METHODS

The method of this research was quantitative because it used data in the form of numbers. According to (Sugiyono 2013), quantitative research is based on the positivism paradigm which is logicohypotheco verification based on assumptions about empirical objects. The criteria of the data obtained in this study were valid, reliable, and objective. Meanwhile, based on the analysis, this research includes descriptive and inferential research (Sugiyono 2011).

This type of research was a survey with a psychological approach. The total populations were 154 and the samples were 77 students, it means that the samples were taken from 50% of the population. The sampling technique used in this study was a quota sampling technique. Quota sampling technique was included in the category of consideration sampling

technique because in quota sampling technique was considered representative on a quota basis. This technique was used for consideration of research problems and research objectives (Mustami 2015). The key instrument of this study was a questionnaire. The data collection techniques were questionnaires, observation and documentation. The data analysis technique was carried out by descriptive statistical analysis and inferential statistical analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Self-concept is an understanding or awareness of oneself about self. The quantitative data are as follows:

Table 1. List of Self Concept Frequencies

Item	Alternative Answers									
	SL	%	SR	%	KD	%	JR	%	TP	%
1	53	69%	14	18%	4	5%	2	3%	4	5%
2	40	52%	17	22%	10	13%	4	5%	6	8%
3	19	25%	28	36%	11	14%	8	10%	11	14%
4	20	26%	20	26%	16	21%	7	9%	14	18%
5	10	13%	14	18%	19	25%	6	8%	28	36%
5	40	52%	15	19%	10	13%	4	5%	8	10%
7	15	19%	15	19%	15	19%	7	10%	25	33%
8	9	12%	13	17%	19	25%	9	12%	27	36%
9	13	17%	9	12%	7	10%	6	8%	42	57%
10	49	64%	9	12%	4	5%	5	6%	10	13%
11	7	10%	9	12%	4	5%	6	8%	51	66%
12	35	45%	15	19%	11	14%	4	5%	12	16%
13	10	13%	6	8%	23	30%	15	19%	23	30%
14	23	30%	16	21%	20	26%	6	8%	12	16%
15	8	10%	11	14%	9	12%	10	13%	39	51%
16	13	17%	11	14%	15	19%	13	17%	25	32%
17	20	26%	17	22%	16	21%	9	12%	15	19%
18	13	17%	18	23%	18	23%	12	16%	16	21%
19	17	22%	8	10%	19	25%	14	18%	19	25%
20	14	18%	8	10%	15	19%	16	21%	24	31%
21	33	43%	14	18%	4	5%	7	9%	19	25%
22	12	16%	8	10%	16	21%	7	9%	34	44%
23	36	47%	13	17%	13	17%	6	8%	9	19%
24	26	34%	15	19%	12	16%	5	6%	19	25%
25	48	62%	14	18%	6	8%	5	6%	4	5%
26	9	11%	11	14%	11	14%	16	21%	30	39%

The percentage calculation of each item was recapitulated to determine the categorization of self-concept variables. For more details, it can be described in table form as follows:

Table 2. Recapitulation of Frequency and Percentage of Number of Questionnaire Responses on Self-Concept (Variable X)

Response	Frequency	Percentage	Category	Frequency	Percentage
5	772	40%	Positive	1097	57%
4	325	17%			
3	320	17%	Medium	537	28%
2	217	11%			
1	298	15%	Negative	298	15%
Total	1932	100%	1932	462	100%

The frequency and percentage data of the self-concept variables table showed that there were 26 questionnaire statement items distributed to 77 respondents of Ternate State Islamic Institute students in the high category with a frequency of 1097 or 57%, while the medium category were in the 537 frequency or 28%, and the low category was in the 298 frequency or 15%.

The results of the recapitulation on the self-concept variable showed that the self-concept of the students of Ternate State Islamic Institute was in the medium category because it was between 20.5% -60%, namely 57%.

Several aspects become benchmarks in knowing student self-concepts, namely:

1. Body image or awareness of the body, namely how a person sees himself with the body he has. Based on the results of categorization, the percentage of body image possessed by the students was in the high category, namely 63%. This means that students have high confidence in the shape of their limbs.
2. Ideal self, that is how a person's ideal and expectations about himself. Based on the results of categorization, the percentage of student's ideal self was in the medium category, namely 51%. This means that students do not too confident about their ideals.
3. The social self is how other people perceive themselves. So students know themselves through other people or their friends. Based on the results of the percentage, the students' social self was in the medium category, namely 60%. Therefore, students' understanding of themselves through the assessment of the people around them can be categorized as a medium, it means that the self-understanding of IAIN Ternate students through the assessment of others was still not perfect.
4. Basic self-concept is a person's concept of himself such as his abilities and disabilities, his role and status in his life and values, beliefs, and aspirations. Based on the percentage results, the students' basic self-concept was 49%. Therefore, students' understanding of themselves through their abilities and disabilities, their role and status in life and their values, beliefs, and aspirations could be categorized as a medium, meaning that self-understanding of the students in Ternate State Islamic Institute through their abilities was not yet perfect.
5. Transitory self-concept, meaning that someone has a "self-concept" that one time he holds it, but at another moment, he releases it. This "self-concept" may be fun, but it is also not. The condition is very situational and much influenced by the atmosphere, such as feelings (emotions), or experiences that have passed. Based on the results that the percentage of

students' transitory self-concepts was 62%. Thus, students understanding of themselves through awareness of their feelings could be categorized as high, meaning that the self-understanding of students in Ternate State Islamic Institute has a high awareness about the condition of their feelings.

Several aspects of the self-concept indicated that students of Ternate State Islamic Institute have an awareness or understanding of themselves that on average were in the medium category. Of the five aspects, only the transitory self-concept aspect was in the high category. The high level of self-understanding or self-awareness of the students in Ternate State Islamic Institute through the feelings which they have experienced was due to the clear effect of unpleasant feelings, for example, the feeling which they don't have an important role in class or discussion groups. If students feel that they do not have an important role in a learning activity, they will have awareness so that they will try to change themselves to get an important role and be responsible for the assignments given.

The percentage of self-concept possessed by students of the State Islamic Institute of Ternate was 57%. So the self-concept possessed by students of the State Islamic Institute of Ternate from 77 respondents was in the medium or weak category. Therefore, to build a student self-concept, the Ternate State Islamic Institute must provide mental experts or consultants for students, especially students who have weak self-concepts.

Deviant behaviour can be defined as an action taken to achieve satisfaction both individually and in groups even though it violates the teachings and rules of a particular society or organization. The descriptive statistical data are as follows:

Table 3. List of Students' Deviant Behaviour Frequencies (Y)

Item	Alternative Answers									
	SL	%	SR	%	KD	%	JR	%	TP	%
1	8	10%	6	8%	9	12%	5	6%	49	64%
2	3	4%	5	6%	2	3%	16	21%	51	66%
3	5	6%	7	9%	12	16%	13	17%	40	52%
4	9	12%	7	9%	9	12%	10	13%	42	54%
5	9	12%	3	4%	5	6%	13	17%	47	61%
6	12	16%	6	8%	5	6%	10	13%	44	57%
7	6	8%	9	12%	10	13%	16	21%	36	46%
8	8	10%	6	8%	12	16%	21	27%	30	39%
9	6	8%	10	13%	12	16%	16	21%	33	43%
10	6	8%	7	9%	17	22%	13	17%	34	44%
11	3	4%	6	8%	20	26%	25	32%	23	30%
12	3	4%	2	3%	5	6%	12	16%	55	71%
13	3	4%	16	21%	21	27%	22	29%	15	19%
14	8	10%	6	8%	9	12%	16	21%	38	49%
15	2	3%	14	18%	18	23%	19	25%	24	31%
16	3	4%	6	8%	7	9%	7	9%	54	70%
17	6	8%	7	9%	6	8%	8	10%	50	65%

18	4	5%	2	3%	7	9%	9	12%	55	71%
19	2	3%	5	6%	3	4%	7	9%	60	78%
20	2	3%	5	6%	7	9%	13	17%	50	65%
21	9	12%	5	6%	10	13%	13	17%	40	52%
22	5	6%	4	5%	3	4%	4	5%	61	80%
23	7	9%	2	2%	9	12%	19	25%	40	52%
24	16	21%	6	8%	12	15%	10	13%	33	43%

The percentage calculation result of each item was recapitulated to determine the categorization of the deviant behaviour variable (Y). For more details, it can be described in table form as follows:

Table 4. Frequency and Percentage Recapitulation of the Number of Questionnaire Responses on Deviant Behaviour (Y).

Response	Frequency	Percentage	Category	Frequency	Percentage
5	1004	55%	Positive	1321	72%
4	317	17%			
3	230	12%			
2	152	8%	Medium	382	20%
1	142	8%	Negative	142	8%
Total	1845	100%		1845	100%

The frequency and the percentage data of the Y variable table showed that the three indicators of the questionnaire statements that were distributed to 77 student respondents at Ternate State Islamic Institute were: in the positive category or did not commit violations was in the frequency of 1321 or 72%, while in the medium category or sometimes violating was in the frequency of 382 or 20%, and in the negative category or always committing violations was in the frequency of 142 or 8%, so that the deviant behaviour of students in Ternate State Islamic Institute was low. As for the aspects of deviant behaviour are the following:

1. Minor violations are violations committed by students that can be tolerated due to certain conditions. the percentage of minor violations committed by students of Ternate State Islamic Institute were: In the positive category meant that not committing minor offences was 71%, in the medium category meant that sometimes committing minor offences was 19% and the negative category meant that always committing minor offences was 10%. Therefore, minor violations committed by students was in low categorize.
2. Medium violations are violations committed by students that still need consideration to be tolerated. The percentage of moderate violations committed by students of the State Ternate Islamic Institute was: in the positive category meant not commit moderate violations was 66%, in the medium category meant sometimes committing medium violation was 29% and in the negative category meant always doing medium violations was 5%. Therefore, medium violations committed by students was in low categorize.
3. Serious violations are violations that can threaten the safety of themselves and others that cannot be tolerated. The percentage of serious violations committed by students of Ternate State Islamic Institute was: in the positive category meant never committed serious

violations was 77% from 77 respondents, the moderate category meant sometimes doing the serious violations was 15% from 77 respondents, meanwhile in the negative category meant always commit serious violations were 8% from 77 Respondents. Therefore, serious violations committed by students of Ternate State Islamic Institute was in low categorize.

Some aspects of this deviant behaviour indicate that from the 77 respondents, it was found that 8% always committed violations, 20% sometimes committed violations, and 72% did not commit the violation, therefore it could be said that the deviant behaviour of Ternate State Islamic Institute students is in low categorize.

From the three aspects above, the most often violation found was that students did not comply with the dress code stated in the student code of ethics

After descriptive analysis, the next step was inferential statistical analysis. In the inferential statistical analysis, there were prerequisite and hypothesis test. The prerequisite test was carried out using the normality test and linearity test. The normality test of the self-concept variable on deviant behaviour (Y) aims to see whether the distribution or distribution of data was normal or not. This normality test used the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test with the consideration that the data was interval or ratio scale (quantitative).

Single data has not been grouped in the frequency distribution table, both for n large and n small, where the number of respondents in this study amounted to 77 which meant more than 30, so if referring to some normality test standards, it was said that if the number of respondents (n) is more than 30 then the research data can be assumed to have been normally distributed. For more details, it can be described in table form as follows:

Table 5. One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test
One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		77
Normal Parameters	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	14.47740359
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.083
	Positive	.072
	Negative	-.083
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		.728
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.664

Test distribution was Normal.

Based on the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test table, it was known that the Asymp. Sig (2-tailed) of 0.664 was greater than 0.05. Then referring to the basis of decision making in the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test above, it could be concluded that the data were normally distributed. Therefore, the assumptions or requirements for normality in the simple regression test have been met. The normality test can also be seen with the Histogram and Normal P-P Plot diagram which are shown below:

Figure 1. Histogram of Data Normality Test Results Figure

The histogram image shows that the curve is normal and each part of the curve is filled with a diagram that represents every data obtained. Data normality indicators can also be seen from the following Normal P-P Plot diagram:

Figure 2. Normal P-P Plot Diagram

Based on this figure, it can be said that the Normal P-P Plot Diagram has met the normality assumption seen in the plots following a straight line.

Furthermore, the linearity test between the self-concept variable (X) and deviant behaviour (Y) can be seen in the following table:

Table 6. ANOVA Test for Variables X and Y

			Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Perilaku Menyimpang * Konsep Diri	Between Groups	(Combined)	14644.235	40	366.106	.958	.555
		Linearity	4109.028	1	4109.028	10.750	.002
		Deviation from Linearity	10535.207	39	270.134	.707	.855
	Within Groups		13760.467	36	382.235		
	Total		28404.701	76			

Based on the output above, the Deviation from Linearity Sig value was obtained. 0.885 was greater than 0.05. So it could be concluded that there was a significant linear relationship between the self-concept variable (X) and deviant behaviour (Y). To see a positive or negative relationship between the self-concept variable (X) and deviant behaviour (Y), it could also refer to the scatter plot chart below:

X and Y Scatter Plot Graph

Figure 3. Scatter Plot Graph

Based on the scatter plot chart above, it can be seen that the data plot points formed a straight-line pattern from the bottom left to top right. This shows that there was a linear and positive relationship between the self-concept variable (X) and deviant behaviour (Y).

After the prerequisite test, to find out whether there was an effect of self-concept on deviant behaviour among students of the State Islamic Institute of Ternate, a simple partial

regression test was carried out using SPSS. The results of the simple regression test can be seen in the following:

Table 7. Coefficients Self-Concept and Deviant Behaviour

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	54.691	11.940		4.580	.000
	Konsep Diri	.452	.127	.380	3.562	.001

a. Predictors: (Constant), Self-Concept

Table 7 informs that a = the constant number from unstandardized was 54,691, which the constant number meant that if there is no self-concept (X) then the consistency value of deviant behaviour (Y) is 54,691. b = number of correlation coefficient which the value was 0.452. This figure meant that every 1% addition of self-concept (X), the deviant behaviour will increase by 0.452 so that the regression equation was $Y = 54,691 + 0.452X$. Furthermore, the hypothesis was tested by comparing t_{count} with t_{table} . If the table was analyzed by taking into account the data first, it was $dk = 77 - 1 = 76$ then $dk = 76$ was found in table 0.679. Based on the output, it was known that the t value was $3.562 > 0.679$. So it could be concluded that H_0 was rejected and H_1 was accepted, which means that there was an effect of self-concept (X) on deviant behaviour (Y).

To find out how was the Self-Concept (X) influenced on Deviant Behaviour (Y) in simple linear regression analysis, it could refer to the value of R Square or R^2 contained in the SPSS output in the summary model section with table form as follows:

Table 8. Model Summary of Self-Concept and Deviant Behaviour

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. The error of the Estimate
1	.380 ^a	.145	.133	17.998

Predictors: (Constant), Self-Concept

Based on the output above, it was known that the R Square value was 0.145. This value implied that the influence of self-concept (X) on deviant behaviour (Y) was 14.5% while 85.5% deviant behaviour was influenced by other variables. Therefore it could be concluded that the self-concept (X) affects deviant behaviour with a total effect was 14.5%.

Based on the results of simple linear regression analysis, the results of the R Square value are 0.145. This value implies that the influence of self-concept (X) on deviant behaviour (Y) is 14.5% while 85.5% deviant behaviour was influenced by other variables. Therefore it could be concluded that the self-concept (X) affects deviant behaviour with a total effect of 14.5%.

The supporting research was the research conducted by Dewi (2015) regarding the relationship between self-concept and deviant behaviour of class XI students at SMKN 1 Bagor 2014/2015 academic year. Based on the data analysis result, the calculation with the product-moment formula obtained the calculated r-value was 0.812, while the value of r table = 0.220 (at the significance level $\alpha = 5\%$) and r table = 0.286 (at the significance level $\alpha =$

1%) so that the results The analysis showed that the value of r count (0.812) > r table (0.286) with $\alpha = 1\%$ > r table (0.220 with $\alpha = 5\%$). Because r count > r table, 0.812 > 0.286, it could be concluded that there was a relationship between self-concept and deviant behaviour in class XI students of SMKN 1 Bagor in the 2014/2015 academic year.

Different from the research conducted by Dewi (2015), this was not just looking for a relationship between self-concept variables and deviant behaviour variables, but rather the discovery of the contribution or influence of self-concept on deviant behaviour in students of Ternate State Islamic Institute.

When associated with several theories about self-concept, the influence of self-concept on deviant behaviour among students of Ternate State Islamic Institute was based on following several factors:

1. Students' understanding of their body (body image) was still not fully realized.
2. Student awareness of their future aspirations or hopes has not been optimal.
3. Students' understanding of themselves which comes from the people around them was less than optimal.
4. Student awareness of their abilities and disabilities (basic self) was less than optimal.
5. Students' ability to bring themselves to situations faced that were less than optimal (transitory self).

Based on several factors that cause deviant behaviour related to self-concept, it could be said that the deviant behaviour carried out by students was due to the less than optimal self-concept of the student himself. In accordance with the results of research from 26 statement items distributed to 77 respondents, it was found that the self-concept of the Ternate State Islamic Institute students was in the middle category because it was between 20.5% - 60%, namely 57%. Therefore, psychologically, students of Ternate State Islamic Institute have a weak self-concept, especially those who engage in deviant behaviour.

CONCLUSION

Referring to the discussion previously described, conclusions could be drawn: First, the self-concept of the Ternate State Islamic Institute students was in the middle category because the value range was between 20.5% - 60%, it was 57%. Second, the deviant behaviour of students in Ternate State Islamic Institute was in the low category between the values of 0% - 20%, it was 8%. Third, there was a significant effect of self-concept on deviant behaviour in Ternate State Islamic Institute students, it was 14.5%, the remaining deviant behaviour was influenced by other variables not studied, and it was 85.5%.

REFERENCES

- Agus. 2020. "Analisis Historis Pondok Pesantren Anwaar-UI-Uloom Bontocani, Kabupaten Bone, Provinsi Sulawesi Selatan." *Jurnal Ilmiah Wahana Pendidikan* 6 (1): 65–73.
- Alang, Sattu. 2014. *Mahasiswa dalam Gerakan Sosial: Menyikapi Perilaku dan Mental Mahasiswa UIN Alauddin Makassar dalam Melakukan Demonstrasi*. Makassar: Alauddin University Press.

- Astuti, Ratna Dwi. 2015. "Identifikasi Faktor-faktor yang Mempengaruhi Konsep Diri Siswa Sekolah Dasar Negeri Mendungan I Yogyakarta." *Basic Education* 4 (2).
- Burga, Muhammad Alqadri. 2019a. "Hakikat Manusia sebagai Makhluk Pedagogik." *Al-Musannif* 1 (1): 19–31.
- Burga, Muhammad Alqadri. 2019b. "Kajian Kritis tentang Akulturasi Islam dan Budaya Lokal." *Zawiyah: Jurnal Pemikiran Islam* 5 (1): 1–20.
- Desmita. 2013. *Psikologi Perkembangan*. 8th ed. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Dewi, Avin Kusumaning. 2015. "Hubungan Konsep Diri dengan Perilaku Menyimpang Peserta Didik Kelas XI di SMKN 1 Bagor Tahun Pelajaran 2014/2015." *Skripsi*. Fakultas Keguruan dan Ilmu Pengetahuan, Universitas Nusantara PGRI Kediri.
- Idris, Djamaluddin M, and Usman Usman. 2019. "Peranan Pendidikan Akhlak dalam Mengembangkan Kepribadian Peserta Didik di Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Parepare." *Al-Musannif* 1 (2): 77–95.
- Khon, Abdul Majid. 2012. *Hadis Tarbawi: Hadis-hadis Pendidikan*. Jakarta: Kencana.
- Makbuloh, Deden. 2012. *Pendidikan Agama Islam: Arah Baru Pengembangan Ilmu dan Kepribadian di Perguruan Tinggi*. Jakarta: PT RajaGrafindo Persada.
- Mustami, Muh. Khalifah. 2015. *Metodologi Penelitian Pendidikan*. Yogyakarta: CV Arti Bumi Intaran.
- Myers, David G. 2012. *Social Psychology*. Terj. Aliya Tusyani Dkk., "Psikologi Sosial". Jakarta: Salemba Humanika.
- Santrock, John W. 2011. *Life-Span Development*. New York: McGraw-Hill Companies.
- Sugiyono. 2011. *Statistika untuk Penelitian*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Sugiyono. 2013. *Metode Penelitian Administrasi*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Yusuf, Syamsu, and Juntika Nurihsan. 2005. *Teori Kepribadian*. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya.

